

INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMY

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Abstract: Special attention is paid to the development of the scientific supply system in the agrarian sector in the formation of the innovative economy in our country. The government of the Republic implemented a number of reforms in order to adapt this system to the requirements of the market economy. The main goal of this is to raise the status of scientific support in the agrarian sector, to widely introduce scientific achievements into practice. In this article, suggestions are made on the directions of innovative development of agriculture.

Key words: Economic globalization, innovation, science and technology, innovative activity, innovative risks and dangers, innovative potential, innovative risks, innovative ideas.

The development trend of the world economy testifies that as one of the main factors in ending poverty and hunger, which is increasing in many regions of the planet in all areas and aspects of human society, especially under the influence of global climate change, agricultural products producers, as well as providing services to them in various directions organization of economic activities of subjects on the basis of innovations has gained strategic importance, continuous improvement of this process is becoming a demand of the times.

In the new conditions of economic globalization, the main sign of economic development is changes in the technological method of production and their impact on the economic potential of the entire society. According to most modern researchers, the innovative changes taking place today not only change the productive forces of society, but also represent the central link in the system of socio-economic processes.

In fact, with the Decree of the President of the country No. PF-5853 of October 23, 2019, in the "Concept of the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030", strengthening of the country's food security, development of modern systems of public administration in the network, agrarian a number of tasks, such as gradual diversification of state expenditures aimed at supporting the sector, were defined.

An important aspect of the innovative development system is that it creates new opportunities for the network to grow at a stable high rate in a short period of time in the conditions of the deformation of the economy, the management of innovation processes, and the existence of an information vacuum at the agricultural level. The role of the state in the formation of this system is incomparable. To have extensive information about the scientific and technical capabilities of agricultural producers and best practices in production, to train them in innovative methods of farming, to master the rules of innovation, and to provide consulting services creates conditions to ensure the increase of innovation activity of ASM by giving.

However, it should be recognized that the agrarian sector, due to its sensitivity and dependence on natural and climatic factors, has a number of difficulties in creating and implementing innovations compared to other sectors, and therefore its development on the basis of innovative modernization is unique and appropriate. requires regular improvement of in-depth research and experimental discovery work in innovative areas. In our opinion, the process of creation of science and technical-technological innovations related to the branches of our country's economy, including agriculture, and the development of innovative activities are not within the narrow scope of our republic, but in harmony with the achievements of the innovative activities of foreign countries with industrial development in these areas. It is advisable to conduct it in this way.

The innovation process in the agricultural sector is a set of activities related to the delivery of qualitatively new products, economic mechanisms, specific

organizational, technical or technological ideas, created on the basis of scientific achievements, to direct use in production. Economic growth in the agrarian sector of the republic is mainly due to the production of import-substituting products and the development of entrepreneurship. However, the development of the innovative process in the areas based on scientific agrarian technology in the network is not at the level of demand. This is adversely affected by the lack of economic, financial, and legal bases for innovation risk management in the network, ways to increase the effectiveness of innovations, assessment of innovation risks and risks, innovation potential in accordance with existing conditions, based on the characteristics of the network.

In the conditions of the activity of a large number of farmers and farms producing agricultural products, the formation of the agrarian innovation market and the characteristics and directions of its activity, the collection of accurate data, their processing, and the use of the obtained conclusions in the conditions of lack of knowledge, there is an attempt to implement scientific developments as an innovative project. This leads to a decrease in the economic, technical and technological, ecological effectiveness of innovative ideas. In our opinion, the market of innovative ideas in the agricultural sector develops primarily depending on the level of formation of the "innovative environment" in the country.

In the market environment, innovative ideas are a commodity and can only be sold if there is a demand for it. The author of an innovative idea is interested not only in selling his project at a profit, but also in receiving income from the result of this project. Therefore, the innovative idea must have a specific owner (person with copyright). Such a system is not always available. Our existing laws allow registration of innovative ideas as objects of intellectual property within the republic and guarantee author's rights in their use.

The liberalization of the economy is directly related to the reduction of the state's intervention in the production and financial activities of economic entities. In

order for a farmer to become a real buyer of innovative ideas as an entrepreneur, his economic freedom must first expand. In this mainly:

- to expand the possibility of full ownership of the farmer's means of production, grown products and generated profits;
- increasing the level of freedom in determining the composition of crops and implementing agrotechnical measures;
- freedom to choose a product sales channel and set a price;
- to create an opportunity to freely purchase products from the resource market in a competitive environment;
- to expand the opportunity to purchase services that are acceptable in terms of quality and price from the market of services in a competitive environment;
- to implement measures to create the opportunity to sell products to processors in a competitive environment;
- the production of products capable of meeting the demand of the growing market should be based on the introduction of modern techniques, new varieties of crops, and agro-technological innovations.

The above circumstances require a specific approach to the development of innovation in agriculture at the early stages of the development of market relations. Now, if we approach the issue from the point of view of the conditions formed for the development of the market of innovative ideas in the agriculture of our republic, as the experience of the transition economy countries shows, the introduction of new economic mechanisms in the organization and management of production "test and errors" style.

Another problem is the efficient use of the harvested product, the development of the processing industry, and the expansion of the production of various consumer goods, in addition to the above-mentioned measures for agricultural production and market innovation. This increases the efficiency of agricultural production and also

increases the competitiveness in the domestic market as well as in the foreign market to a certain extent.

The following are the important directions of the innovative policy aimed at the development of agriculture and increasing the efficiency of the activities of farmers and farm entities in it:

- compliance of production volumes of basic food products with medical consumption standards;
- production of promising products of interregional exchange and export value;
- production of products with a high share of added value and economic efficiency;
- products produced in small and large enterprises should be in an acceptable ratio, complementing each other;
- increasing the efficiency of resource use by reducing anthropogenic impact on the ecosystem.

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